

The growth-related effects of 2-(4-isobutylphenyl) propionic acid on *Raphanus sativus*

Ren Hart, Shaaheen Khosrowshahi, Timothy Love, Cole Lyons

The University of North Carolina at Charlotte

BIOL 2140 L-04

Dr. Tuan Cao

April 27, 2022

Abstract

Ibuprofen, also known as 2-(4-isobutylphenyl) propionic acid, is a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug commonly used for the treatment of pain in humans. The significance of this research is that plants are crucial to our society, environment and survival. We need plants for oxygen, to fix carbon from our atmosphere, and for food amongst many other things. Knowing that water is such a valuable resource to plants and their growth, it is also important to know if there are treatments that could purify water better for better plant growth as a result. Especially if those ways are safe for the environment and for herbevorial consumption. Our experiment evaluated the growth, yield, and morphology effects of ibuprofen on *Raphanus sativus* (commonly known as a French Breakfast Radish). To evaluate ibuprofen's effects, we grew radishes from seeds. We treated our radish groups with varying concentrations of ibuprofen in the water supply, and then measured the yield and weights of the mature

bulbs after five weeks of growth. The radishes in the control group were treated with water containing no ibuprofen. By the end of the experiment it was found that the higher the concentration of ibuprofen, the lower the number and the weight of radish harvests.

Introduction

Plants are arguably the most important organism on the face of the earth as they provide us with the oxygen that we need, fix carbon dioxide from the atmosphere, and provide us with food and nutrients. In order for plants to be able to sustain themselves, they need water. Water provides the electrons during photosynthesis in order to create glucose.. Plants need a good source of water, nutrients, and light in order to grow. The roots of the plant absorb these nutrients and move water through certain channels to filter its way throughout the cell in order for the plant to grow as well as perform different activities and processes, like producing sugars (Ingestad & Lund, 2008). But what would happen if something was added to the water that the plants need? Would this harm the plants? Would this hinder/help their growth? In this experiment we analyze the effects of different concentrations of ibuprofen (2-(4-isobutylphenyl) propionic acid) in water on French Breakfast Radishes (*Raphanus sativus*). Thirty radish seeds will be planted for the control and for each concentration of ibuprofen. A control will be set in place which contains radishes that are grown with pure water. We then will set watering concentrations of 250 ppm, 500 ppm, and 1000 ppm. When watering the radishes, it is important to keep the concentrations the same throughout the experiment to accurately reflect the advantages or disadvantages that ibuprofen in water affects the growth of the radishes. We know that ibuprofen is used as a pain reliever or anti-inflammatory in humans, so what would be the effect on other organisms? Plants need substances like Nitrogen and Phosphorus in order to grow and be healthy (Singh, Chandra & Goel, 2012). A rich soil environment will help complete this task. The question is are there certain chemical compounds or substances that could further help plants grow that we don't know about or are not currently using? Radishes were grown with different concentrations of ibuprofen as well as a control group of radishes grown with only water to analyze the potential effects. Our hypothesis is that the 2-4-isobutylphenyl propionic acid would have a

negative effect on the growth of the French Breakfast Radishes. The two predictions would be that indeed, the radishes would have trouble growing as the concentration of ibuprofen increased, or the growth rate of the radishes would increase as the concentrations of ibuprofen increased.

Methods

Subjects

The species *Raphanus sativus* (French Breakfast Radish) was selected as the subject of this experiment. A total of 120 seeds were planted. They were divided into 4 groups. The control group, which used filtered water only, followed by three experimental groups with 250ppm, 500ppm and 1000ppm Ibuprofen concentrations in the water supply, respectively. Each group consisted of two pots, with 15 seeds per pot (30 seeds per group).

Environment and Supplies

Seeds and soil were bought and planted in starter trays. Each group of 3 seeds were planted 1 inch into the soil. The trays used consisted of 3 rows of 4 cells, with a total of 12 cells. After the planting step was done, solutions of 250ppm, 500ppm and 1000ppm of water and ibuprofen were made using dye free, generic ibuprofen and filtered water. The ibuprofen was mixed using a 1000(mL) Milliliter beaker, and a magnetic stir bar. 15mls of filtered water was added to each cell within the control group, 15mls of the 250ppm ibuprofen-water solution was added to each cell within the second group and 500ppm and 1000ppm respectively in the same order. All groups were kept in a controlled environment with a temperature between 65-70 Degrees Fahrenheit, relative Humidity of 50%, and 600 PPF of light for 12 hours/day for 7 days. On the 7th day, 5 cells were picked randomly from each tray (10 cells total from each group) and moved into bigger pots resulting in 8 pots each containing 5 seeds, (2 pots total, 10 cells total), for each group. They were watered every three days using 1L (1Liter), of water, with water only, 250ppm, 500ppm, and 1000ppm, concentrations respectively, for 28 days.

Assessments and Measures

On harvest day, all radishes were harvested and separated into their respective groups. We cut the leaves off each radish, washed them, and weighed them individually. We entered individual radish weights into Microsoft Excel under their respective groupings, and used excel functions to calculate the average, sum, and count of each group. Finally, we used the data analysis tool to conduct an Analysis of variance - ANOVA analysis which gave us the data.

Flowchart

Results

After examination of each group's harvest weight, there was a noticeable weight difference between the groups with ibuprofen contaminated water supply and also compared to the control group. This also applies to the counts of the harvests from each group. The control group had only given 22 Radishes. The mean weight of the radish bulbs in the control group was 8.5g. The radishes in the three experimental groups were treated with water containing ibuprofen concentrations of 250ppm, 500ppm, and 1000ppm. The mean weights of these three groups were 8.3g, 6.5g, and 1.8g, respectively. The total weight for all radish bulbs grown in the water-only control group was 187.6g. The total weight for the test groups were 184.3g, 144.2g, and 39.7g, respectively. ANOVA analysis showed statistical differences between the sample means (95% Confidence Interval [CI], $F[4.915]$; $P=0.003$). Upon visual inspection,

there were no significant morphological differences. *Raphanus sativus* radish growth and overall crop yield was affected by ibuprofen concentrations in the water, with gross yield and average weight decreasing in a stepwise fashion as the concentrations increased. No morphological differences were noted upon visual inspection, however histological sampling would be required for a full analysis of plant morphology.

ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	650.071364	3	216.690455	4.95159568	0.00325366	2.71322713
Within Groups	3675.98636	84	43.7617424			
Total	4326.05773	87				

ANOVA analysis showed statistical differences between the sample means (95% Confidence Interval [CI], F[4.915]; P=0.003).

Water	250ppm	500ppm	1000ppm
31	25.9	22.7	19.5
19.2	18	20.6	10.5
13.8	17.1	18.6	5.2
12.1	14.2	17.6	3.4
11.8	13.9	14.1	0.6
11.7	13.8	10.7	0.5
10.9	13.4	10.7	0
10.8	11.7	6.5	0
9.4	10.9	4.9	0
8.1	10.3	4.4	0
6.9	7	4.4	0
6.8	6.3	3.7	0
6.7	6	3.2	0

4.6	4.6	0.8	0
3.8	3.4	0.7	0
3.8	2.8	0.6	0
3.3	2	0	0
3.2	1.4	0	0
3	1.1	0	0
2.8	0.5	0	0
2.3	0	0	0
1.6	0	0	0

COUNT	COUNT	COUNT	COUNT
22	20	16	6
WATER	250ppm	500ppm	1000ppm
Water	250ppm	500ppm	1000ppm
187.6	184.3	144.2	39.7
AVERAGE	AVERAGE:	AVERAGE:	AVERAGE:
8.527272727	8.37727273	6.55454545	1.80454545

Control STD: 6.7855 | Control ME: 1.45 | Whole STD: 7.05 | Whole Margin of Error: 0.7517

Total Mean: 6.041304348

Figure 1. designed to demonstrate the difference in the number of radishes that have grown in each group. The Controlled group, with regular water supply had the most number of harvests (22) , the second group (250ppm) had only 20 radishes as the result. The number of radishes produced in the third group (500ppm) was 16 and finally for the 1000ppm water supply we only harvested 6. The slope of the line is a straight line with a negative slope.

Figure 2. Demonstrates the comparison between the total harvest weight of each group with different ibuprofen concentrations. The total weight of harvest in the control group was 187.6 grams and it's also the maximum point on the graph. The second group (250ppm) with 184.3 grams total weight is next. Followed by the third group (500ppm) with a total harvest weight of 144.2. And finally the last group with 1000ppm ibuprofen concentration with a total harvest weight of 39.7 grams

Figure 3. The purpose of Figure 3 is to demonstrate the AVERAGE radish weight differences between the groups with different ibuprofen concentrations. The highest bar belongs to the controlled group with a weight average of 8.52 grams. The lowest bar belongs to the group with 1000ppm ibuprofen concentration with the weight average of 1.80 grams. Group 250ppm and 500ppm each have a total weight average of 8.37 grams and 6.55 grams respectively

Figure 4. A complimentary graph for Figure 1 in a pie chart format for the purpose of better understanding the differences in radish quantity in each group with different ibuprofen concentrations

Discussion

The purpose of this research was to see the effects of ibuprofen on plant growth. We wanted to set up a control of radishes grown with pure water and compare it to radishes grown with increasing concentrations of ibuprofen in the water supply. Our hypothesis was that the radishes subjected to ibuprofen would have decreased weight in a stepwise fashion, decreasing in weight as the amount of

ibuprofen in the water increased. As we can see from these results ibuprofen had a negative, linear relationship with radish weight. Roots work in tandem with rhizomes to pull water into the plant and navigate that water to where it is needed in the plant. Roots absorb the water into the plant while rhizomes pull water up the plant shoots into other parts of the plant (SEB Weisner, JA Strand, 1996). By analyzing the results of this research it seems that this process could have been negatively affected by the concentrations of ibuprofen in the experimental water supplies. Certain chemicals and fertilizers are currently used in crops to maximize soil potential and maximize plant growth. These substances make nutrients in soil more readily accessible for plant functions (D Davidson, FX Gu, 2012). We needed to know if ibuprofen, which is something readily accessible to humans, would have this effect on plants. One potential followup study would be to evaluate the effects of ibuprofen on growth of other plants, or possibly on animals. While performing the ANOVA analysis, we found that the control standard deviation was 6.7855, control margin of error was 1.45, the whole standard deviation was 7.05, the whole margin of error was 0.7517, and the total mean was 6.041304348. ANOVA analysis also showed statistical differences between the sample means (95% Confidence Interval [CI], $F[4.915]$; $P=0.003$). There were many experimental errors, boiling water was poured onto the plants repeatedly, the amount of space each radish had to grow was very limited as too many radishes were planted per pot, and the study size was fairly small with only a few radishes even surviving to the harvest stage in the 1000ppm groups. A good follow up study to this research would be to test different concentrations of fertilizers and chemicals that we currently use in crop production to determine at what rate the fertilizers stop assisting plant growth and when they begin to poison the crops. This would be important because as consumers, we are unaware of how much fertilizers and chemicals are used on our foods before we eat them. The significance as to why this research is important is that plants are very valuable to our society and everyday living. We need plants for oxygen, to fix carbon from our atmosphere, and for food amongst many other things. Knowing that water is such a valuable resource to plants and their growth, it is also important to know if there are treatments that we could do to water to help that process. Especially if those ways are safe for the environment and for herbevorial consumption.

Acknowledgments

We would like to thank Lowe's for guiding us through planting the seeds, Walgreens for the dye-free Ibuprofen purchase, Cole for providing the space for conducting the experiment and Courtney (TA) for giving feedback and guiding us through the process and helping us finalize the project.

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